

Technical query to CMD-3: public convention and covariance use in a $\pi^+\pi^-$ window-mode diagnostic

Dale James Raymond, Melbourne, Australia; ORCID 0009-0001-1682-8529

19 May 2026

Project record: doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/CKJBU; release record: doi:10.5281/zenodo.20279233

Purpose. This one-page note is for technical checking only. It does not ask CMD-3 to endorse the interpretation. The question is whether the public CMD-3 form-factor/cross-section information is being used with the correct covariance and convention for a bin-level diagnostic of how $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ inputs propagate into muon- $g - 2$ Euclidean windows.

Input and convention used. CMD-3 input: ancillary $|F_\pi|^2$ data associated with PRD 109, 112002 / arXiv:2302.08834. I convert to the bare $\pi^+\pi^-$ cross section using

$$\sigma_{\pi\pi}^0(s) = \frac{\pi\alpha^2}{3s} \beta_\pi^3 |F_\pi(s)|^2, \quad (1)$$

and intend this to match the a_μ convention with vacuum polarization removed and final-state radiation included. The paper labels the 2013 scan as RHO2013 and the 2017–2018 scan as RHO2018; the ancillary file I parsed also contains LOW2020 threshold points. BaBar, KLOE-combined and BESIII are placed on a common 1 MeV grid over 0.327–0.920 GeV. SND is used only in the separate band-integrated 0.6–0.9 GeV benchmark.

Diagnostic numbers before CMD-3 technical feedback.

Quantity	Current value
Common-grid CMD-3 minus rest shift in (ID,FULL)	$(7.431, 23.686) \times 10^{-10}$
Cosine with leading between-mode direction	0.9992
Fixed-direction variance ratio after removing CMD-3	0.234
Variance reduction after removing CMD-3	76.6%
Band benchmark, CMD-3, 0.6–0.9 GeV	389.98 ± 0.50
Band benchmark, non-CMD-3 rest, 0.6–0.9 GeV	370.32 ± 1.20
Required CMD-3-to-rest correction, FULL-weighted, 0.6–0.9 GeV	about -5.21%

The quoted band uncertainty for CMD-3 is not treated as definitive; it is precisely the covariance point I want to check.

Specific questions.

1. Is the VP/FSR convention above correct for comparison to BaBar/KLOE/BESIII a_μ inputs?
2. For an HVP/window comparison in the ρ region, should the public diagnostic use RHO2018 only, RHO2013 only, LOW2020 threshold points where relevant, or a particular CMD-3 combined construction?
3. Is there a public CMD-3 covariance matrix or correlation prescription for the ancillary $|F_\pi|^2$ or converted cross-section points?
4. Which systematic components should be treated as fully correlated across energy, partially correlated, or pointwise for an integral over 0.6–0.9 GeV?
5. Are there known cross-correlations between RHO2013/RHO2018, energy-scale effects, or radiative-correction correlations that would materially change the integrated uncertainty or line-shape comparison?